

Development of Career Opportunities and Dual Career Development among Students in Secondary Schools in Sebei Sub-Region

¹Yapsoyekwo Justine, ²Olivia Banja Nassaka, ³Muweesi Charles,
⁴Nambale Moses Geoffrey

¹Uganda Christian University Mukono

²Uganda Christian University Mukono

³Busitema University

⁴Uganda Management Institute

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078279>

Published Date: 07-November-2023

Abstract: Dual careers have become a relevant matter in the world of work as one of the tools that can improve social life. In that regard, this study sought to examine the influence of development of career opportunities on dual career development among students. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with both qualitative and quantitative approaches in which a population of 360 people involving headteachers, deputy headteachers, Directors of Studies, Career guidance teachers, Games teachers; Sports officers; and students who have been involved in games and sports in the schools were targeted. The study used a sample of 186 people selected using purposive, simple random and cluster sampling techniques. Data was collected using a validated and pre-tested self-administered questionnaire and interview guide. Analysis of the quantitative data collected was done using descriptive and inferential statistics generated by the SPSS; while analysis of the qualitative data was done using thematic and content analysis.

The findings of the study revealed that for development of career opportunities and dual career development; $R^2 = .227$, $F=53.669$, $Sig= .000 < .05$ for academic career and $R^2 = .299$, $F=78.211$, $Sig = .000 < .05$ for sports career. The study concluded that development of career opportunities had a higher influence for sports than for academic career development. The study finally recommends that career guidance teachers need to be appropriately informed about the processes that lead to development of career opportunities among individuals.

Keywords: Development of Career Opportunities, Dual Career Development, Students Sebei Sub-Region.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background

According to the European Union (2012), development of career opportunities is a broad educational initiative that influences instruction across all grade levels and subject areas. As a result, development of career opportunities should serve as a means of bridging information, skills, life preparation, and career preparation (O'Neil et al,2013). According to Lemeni and Mihalcea (2005), development of career opportunities is an educational intervention created in advance of the skills and abilities required for the growth and management of beginning careers.

The formation of a dual career, on the other hand, combines both academic and athletic experiences, as well as a job or line of work mixed with participation in sports (Swann, Moran, & Piggott, 2015). The goal of dual career development, as consistently stated in policy statements, is to help students develop the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes necessary to

comprehend and succeed both inside and outside of the classroom, supporting both personal and societal economic performance (OECD, 2010).

Dual careers are still quite new, even though career education has long been practiced in Uganda. However, it has been noted that Ugandans continue to change careers. It is wise to give studies on dual careers and career education considerable thought. The current state of dual careers and career education in Uganda is discussed in this subsection.

The Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) in Uganda has as its vision “*Quality Education and Sports for All,*” and its mission “*To provide for, support, guide, coordinate, regulate, and promote delivery of quality Education and Sports to all persons in Uganda; for national integration, individual, and national development*” (ESSP, 2017). This suggests that Uganda’s MoES takes into account the dual career development of all learners, specifically academic and athletic. The ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20 has only designated 32 schools as sports centers, nevertheless. As a result, career education is not typically prioritized in schools for the benefit of students. Therefore, it is still unclear how the learners’ development of dual careers was affected by the lack of emphasis placed on careers education.

As was already indicated, the MoES in Uganda is a dual ministry since, in line with its mission, it aims to help students advance both their academic and athletic abilities. In an ideal world, the educational system would prepare students for careers in both athletics and academia. There is no official training for service providers in Uganda’s educational curriculum, despite the fact that career education services were created in the USA more than 100 years ago. The educational programs in Uganda are structured to get students ready for the next level of learning. Prior to 2020, Uganda’s secondary education curriculum gave priority to topic knowledge at the expense of helping students develop marketable and transferrable skills and competences (NCDC, 2020). The previous secondary education curriculum was initially created for a select group of exceptional kids headed for careers in the public sector. As a result, every learner will be able to acquire understandings and skills in accordance with his or her capacity, according to NCDC (2020). NCDC further affirms that the new curriculum will be designed so that it gives every learner the chance to gain the knowledge, skills, and attitudes they need as well as the opportunity to receive the proper acknowledgment for their accomplishments while they are in school (NCDC, 2020).

Career instructors have been in charge of career education in secondary schools in Uganda up until the introduction of the new lower secondary school curriculum. These educators work to provide knowledge on the following topics and frequently take part in activities that are linked to them, including assessing career needs, creating career chances, fusing student needs with professional opportunities, and routine monitoring (NCDC, 2017). Their level of interaction with the kids differs from one school to the next due to a variety of circumstances, including time constraints, facilitation, and support from other stakeholders, to name a few. The teachers work hard to help the students establish personal development plans that should be founded on their beliefs, aspirations, and self-awareness.

Statement of the Problem

Despite support provided in development of career opportunities in secondary schools, dual career development remains a significant obstacle. Due to its mission of offering top-notch sports and education to all students, Uganda’s Ministry of Education and Sports supports the conventional dual career growth. In order to help learners transition from one career to another in the 21st century successfully and without major obstacles, dual career development is the way to go. Secondary schools students with development of career opportunities through their careers teachers in this regard. However, a lot of Sebei students have had trouble preparing for both a career in academics and a career in sports. Numerous students are still struggling with the issue of dual career development, and the majority of them are unable to conduct efficient self-evaluations, explore opportunities, identify career opportunities, integrate their goals with employee needs, or conduct routine choice monitoring (OECD, 2018). There are research on sports and athletics (Taras, 2005; Yiannakis and Melnick, 2001), but there is little information on how support in development of career opportunities affects the growth of dual careers in Uganda, particularly in the Sebei sub-region. Before students enter the final stages of their education, secondary schools should ensure that there is a balanced progression of their careers. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate how support in development of career opportunities influences dual career development among students in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region.

Purpose

To establish the influence of supporting development of career opportunities on dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Significance of Study

The results of this study may help stakeholders in different ways; for instance: It will assist the Ministry of Education and Sports in making sure that Uganda has the chance to create an advanced secondary level curriculum, which will be essential in shaping young people into become more independent, proactive professionals capable of competing for jobs right out of school, especially if they cannot afford to pursue a more rigorous study at the university level. It will assist the District Education Officers in promoting the National Curriculum Development Centre's (NCDC) curriculum in order to encourage dual career development among Ugandan youth. For better outcomes in both academics and athletics, it will allow school officials to give their kids' dual career development first priority. The findings might serve as a foundation for the academia.

Scope of the Study

The study was done in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region of eastern Uganda, close to the Kenya-Uganda border. The region is located 295 kilometers (183 miles) northeast of Kampala, the capital city of Uganda, along 01 24N, 34 27E. Although it is a mountainous area with challenging terrain, it is well known for producing some of the best athletes in the nation. The Sebei sub-region was chosen for this study because it has recently produced the top athletes, both men and women, and because many students there are experimenting with dual career development, particularly in athletics. The study focused on creating career opportunities on dual career development among secondary school students in the Sebei sub-region. This was due to the USPA (2019) report's indication that dual career development in secondary schools was weak. The period from 2015 to 2021 was considered for the study because this was the period that witnessed renewed efforts in career education with challenges in dual career development (Otwine and Oonyu, 2018).

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1.1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Cosh and Tully (2014); and Rugangila (2019).

Theoretical Review

The study adopted Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory

Albert Bandura proposed the Social Cognitive Theory in 1986 as an expansion of the prior Social Learning Theory he had created in 1977. According to the idea, learning can be partially attributed to observing others while taking into account social interactions, personal experiences, and outside media influences. According to the hypothesis, when individuals watch a model engage in an action and experience the results, they retain the chronology of events and make use of it to direct future behavior. The Social Cognitive Theory is put out from an agent perspective, which contends that people are self-developing, self-regulating, self-reflective, and proactive rather than just being formed by their environments or inner forces (Pajares, 2009). According to Pajares (2009), human agency primarily takes three forms: individual, proxy, and collective. Individual agency refers to a person's direct influence on the environment, while proxy agency refers to another person's efforts to protect the individual's interests.

The central idea of social cognitive theory, according to Bandura (1988), is that information is acquired or learned by observation of models. The models may come from media sources or interpersonal imitation. Effective modeling offers overarching principles and methods for handling various circumstances. According to the idea, learning is most likely to happen when the observer and the model have a high degree of identification and the observer also has a high level of self-efficacy (Urich, 2017). Self-efficacy is the degree to which a person has confidence in their ability to learn a specific skill. Self-efficacy beliefs influence behavior through intervening motivational, cognitive, and affective processes, making them a significant set of proximal determinants of human motivation, affect, and action (Bandura, 1989).

Supporting development of some behaviour enables the individual being supported to experience a 1:1 likeness with the model, which may increase the likelihood that the observer will carry out the modeled behavior (Bandura, 1988). People are more likely to imitate the behaviour of someone they can relate to. The likelihood that the observer learns and imitates the modeled behavior increases with the number of similarities or emotional connections that are seen between them. SCT is frequently used in media studies as it relates to sports, health, education, and other topics. For instance, Hardin and Greer in 2009 researched the gender-typing of sports within the theoretical framework of social cognitive theory and proposed that gender perception of sports among American college students was highly influenced by gender-role socialization and sports media use. Therefore, Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory was appropriate in predicting the results of this study on career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory

The notion of career development examines ways to enhance professional development, career trajectories, and overall job satisfaction. Understanding professional development theory can be a crucial first step in figuring out your fundamental values, aptitudes, and chosen route. While different career development theories make different claims, all of them stress the value of forming meaningful professional ambitions and cultivating a positive emotional relationship with one's work. The developmental hypothesis was developed by Donald Super on the premise that your self-perception evolves. The way a person values their profession and the goals they set is shaped by time and experience. According to this view, a person's lifetime constitutes their entire "career." Five stages of career growth were identified by Super: Growth, Exploration, Establishment, Maintenance and Decline.

Super believed that how satisfied people were with their careers depended on how they perceived themselves at each of these five stages of development. A work-life balance, for example, may be more important at the maintenance stage than in the establishment stage. Even if a person's career doesn't change, experience and time might change how they perceive their area of work. This study on development of career opportunities and dual career development among students in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region was appropriately supported by Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory.

2. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Development of career opportunities is regarded as the major psycho-social task of adolescence. In order to create and develop an identity, an individual is required to both explore potentialities and imagine a future (Erikson, 2018). Developing a future perspective is entwined with narrating one's identity and its development because constructing stories about the future selves involves creating ideas about who we are and what kind of life roles we want to inhabit (McAdams, 2008). As development of opportunities shape students' self-understandings of what is possible or desirable, they are central to young people's career decision-making. When older adolescents are asked about their future goals and hopes, most often they appear to follow culturally accepted responses (Fivush, 2010; Nurmi, 2004) to prioritize their career identities (i.e., education and work).

Contemporary culture provides a set of 'scripts' of what is expected from a young person and these scripts not only guide young people's personal story construction, but also serve a prescriptive function of how a 'good' life should look like (e.g., when one should graduate from school, get married, and begin a career path). Fivush (2010) asserted that cultural scripts differentiate possibilities based on gender (among other sociocultural characteristics) and serve as a lens for evaluating biographical events and making meaning of an experience. Initially, young people develop an understanding of values, meaning, and identity options from their home environment. Later, peers, role models, school and other learning environments play an increasingly important role (Nurmi, 2004). For young people who enjoy sport, the stories shared by famous athletes often become exemplary scripts. Within most sporting communities, there exist sub-cultural stories that inform youth athletes' interpretations of certain events, expectations of themselves, and their general understanding of the

shape of a successful life. Thus, ‘exemplary life stories’ (Spector-Mersel, 2006) provide narrative plots and discursive resources for constructing a self-story.

Among the many stories that may be created, ‘master narratives’ are those which, by their prevalence, are deemed to reflect the beliefs and values of a given community (Fivush, 2010; Hammack, 2008). Although master narratives are discursive structures, they function as enduring parts of structural marginalisation in a cultural community or society at large (Fivush, 2010; McLean & Syed, 2016). For example, Douglas and Carless (2009) identified three cultural narratives circulating within sport – the performance, discovery, and relational narratives. As students scripts these stories provide a plot and template that shape elite athletes’ life stories and have different implications for their identities, life choices and psychological health. The authors described a performance narrative as a storyline where “winning, results, and achievements are pre-eminent and link closely to the storyteller’s mental well-being, identity, and self-worth” (p. 215). That is, the athlete’s self and identity are on the line every time he or she fails. The performance narrative’s troubling implications for athletes’ health and psycho-social well-being have been well documented in the sport psychology literature (Carless & Douglas, 2013; Douglas & Carless, 2015; McGannon et al., 2019). However, not all athletes’ experiences align with master narratives and, to make meaning of these ‘unfitting’ experiences, they may need to construct or adopt an alternative narrative, which either diverges from or even resists the master narrative (Carless & Douglas, 2013).

When a person’s experiences do not fit with the group’s normative projections of the life course, then the identity work is to mend the biographical rupture by making sense of that deviation. For example, in a recent study of elite athlete mother identity, McGannon et al. (2019) explicated the complicated processes of re-configuring the performance narrative meanings through alternative narrative resources in the cultural sphere which ideals and values construct sport and motherhood as incompatible.

Narrating a life story is a complex social practice involving selection of tell-able episodes and reflectively bracketing and organizing them into broader themes and story-lines. Bamberg and Georgakopoulou (2008) contend that adolescents may have limited narrative resources nor enough practice for this task. Although their stories are often small interactions about mundane events, they are important sites for testing out their identities (Bamberg, 2011). Thus, through a life history where individuals share stories across different time frames, there is potential for young athletes to develop and extent their narrative resources as well as ‘practice’ using them from a particular identity position.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with both qualitative and quantitative paradigms was used. Kothari (2006) affirms that the main idea behind using this type of design is to better define an opinion, attitude, or behaviour held by a group of people on a given subject. This is exactly what this study set out to establish about development of career opportunities and dual career development among students in secondary schools.

Population and Sampling Techniques

The target population for the study consisted of various categories of people who included members of the headteachers (15) and deputy headteachers (15) of the selected secondary schools, Directors of Studies (15, DOS), career guidance teachers (15), games teachers (30), sports officers (03), students who have been involved in games and sports (267) in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. The total target population of study constituted of 360 people. Basing on the Glenn (1992) sampling table, the sample of the study constituted of 186 respondents who were sampled using purposive and cluster sampling techniques. Table 1.1 presents the summary of the population, sample size and sampling techniques used in the study.

Table 1.1: Population, Sample Size and Sampling Techniques used in the Study

Category	Population	Sample Size	Sampling Technique
Sports Officers	03	03	Census
Headteachers	15	08	Purposive
Deputy Headteachers	15	08	Purposive
Directors of Studies	15	08	Purposive
Teachers (CG, Games/Sports)	45	23	Cluster Sampling
Students	267	136	Cluster Sampling
Total	360	186	

Source: District Education Registries for Kapchorwa, Kween and Bukwo (2021)

The study used two methods of data collection, the questionnaire (survey) method and the interview method. The instruments of data collection were the self-administered questionnaires, interview guides and checklists. In this study, closed questions were constructed on a four-point pre-coded Likert scale. To a small extent, open-ended questions were used to generate more details on the variables under study. This design of the questionnaire is appropriate as supported by Saunders et al (2009); Dillman (2000); de Vaus (2002) who stated that closed questions provide a number of alternative answers from which a respondent is instructed to choose. In this respect, pre-tested SAQs were used to collect quantitative data from the headteachers and teachers, and students who have been involved in games and sports in the schools under study.

The interview guide was used to collect data from the Sports Officers, headteachers, deputy headteachers and directors of studies because these are often busy people and yet are custodians of information on issues under study. Using interview guides also helps to minimize non-response and maximize quality of data collected (Creswell, 2014). Furthermore, use of interview guides can solicit information that can be considered sensitive (Creswell, 2014) and respondents may need probing and follow-up on some issues under investigation.

Quality Control

To ensure quality control, the instruments of data collection were tested for validity and reliability. The research instrument was validated through consultation with supervisors and computation of the Content Validity Index (CVI) was done to ascertain appropriateness of validity. Any proposed corrections were made to improve on the validity. On the other hand, the reliability of the instrument was assessed by first piloting the instrument with a few respondents who were not part of the final sample and using the split-half technique, the reliability coefficient by Chronbach as outlined below.

According to Hammersley (1987), an instrument is valid or true if it represents accurately those features of the phenomena that it is intended to describe, explain or theorize. Insofar, validity is concerned with two main issues: whether the instruments used for measurement are accurate and whether they are actually measuring what they want to measure (Winter, 2000). Ritchie and Lewis (2003) indicated that the validity of research is conceived as the precision or correctness of the research finding. In this study, validity of the instrument was assessed through consultation with supervisors and rating the items and then computing the Content Validity Index (CVI) which was found to be 0.81. According to George and Mallery (2003) scale, a value of 0.8 - 0.89 means good validity. Thus since the CVI obtained was 0.81, it meant that the validity of the instrument was good and worthy for use in data collection based on the George and Mallery (2003) scale.

Smith et al., (2008) define reliability as the extent to which data collection techniques or analysis procedures yield consistent findings. Marshall and Rossman (1999); and Seale (1999) argued that the absolute replication of studies is very difficult to achieve since they reflect realities at the time they were collected and in a situation which is likely to change. A good practice of reliability can be enhanced through an aspect of reflexivity, which is showing the audience of research studies as much as possible of the procedures that have led to a particular set of conclusions (Seale, 1999). In this study, the researchers pre-tested the research instrument on a reasonable number of respondents, who were not used in the final data collection process. After pre-testing, the Chronbach's Alpha (α) Coefficient was computed to indicate the level of reliability of the instrument. From the computation, value of Chronbach Alpha obtained was 0.894 and according to George and Mallery (2003) scale, this was interpreted as good reliability.

Data Processing and Analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to compute descriptive statistics i.e. frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. From the descriptive statistic (means) the inferential statistics i.e. simple linear regression was generated. For qualitative data analysis, collected data were transcribed, coded, categorized and themes built through content analysis. This was meant to enhance readability and understanding of the research findings by a larger public interested in issues of development of career opportunities and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Uganda.

Ethical Considerations

In terms of ethical considerations, the researcher first had to be cleared by the ethical committee of the university and then obtain an introductory letter to the field. It was also necessary to seek consent from the respondents before questionnaires and interviews were administered. The respondents were also assured of anonymity and confidentiality of all the

information provided in the introductory part of the self-administered questionnaire. During interviews, the researcher ensured that items in the interview guide or the questionnaire did not infringe on the personality of the respondents. Due to COVID-19 pandemic at the time of data collection, the researcher ensured that use of masks, regular sanitizing and social distancing were strictly observed by all who were involved in the data collection process. Last but not least, the respondents were assured that the information being collected were strictly used for the sake of the study.

4. STUDY FINDINGS

Demographic Data of Respondents

The respondents were required to indicate their sex, age bracket, level of education and marital status. The detailed results about each characteristic are presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Demographic Data of Respondents

Category	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	122	65.9
Female	63	34.1
Total	185	100.0
Age Bracket		
20-29 Years	126	68.1
30-39 Years	23	12.4
40-49 Years	24	13.0
Above 50 Years	12	6.5
Total	185	100.0
Education Level		
Diploma	20	10.8
Degree	30	16.2
Masters	12	6.5
A-level	123	66.5
Total	185	100.0
Responsibility		
Deputy Headteachers	12	6.5
Headteachers	8	4.3
Teachers	42	22.7
Students	123	66.5
Total	185	100.0

Source: Primary data (2022)

Out of the 185 respondents who completed the self-administered questionnaires, there were more male than female respondents. According to Table 4.2, 65.9% of the respondents were male while 34.1% of them were female respondents. This implies that in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, more men than women have been deployed to teach the students. From Table 1.2, majority (68.1%) of the respondents were in the age bracket of 20-29 years old while 12.4% were in the age bracket of 30-39 years old. Another 13.0% of them were in the age bracket of 40-49 years while only 6.5% were above 50 years of age. This implied that majority of the respondents were young adults who are often have vibrant interest in career development for their future lives.

The findings also showed that majority (66.5%) of the respondents were of A-level students which was the focus of the study. A-level students were considered because they at a critical stage of career determination as they prepare to tertiary education. Data in Table 1.2 further indicated that 16.2% of the respondents had degrees and 10.8% had diplomas. These were mainly the teachers of games and sports who were also considered vital in provision of data for this study. At least 6.5% of the respondents had masters degrees. These too were teachers that participated in the study. This implies that all the respondents who participated in this study had an appropriate level of education to have a clear understanding of the items in the self-administered questionnaire. Thus, it is presumed that the data they provided can be reliable in making precise conclusions about the study.

Data presented in Table 1.2 also revealed that 66.5% of the respondents were students who formed the biggest proportion of the unit of analysis. Another 22.7% were classroom teachers who also doubled as games/sports teachers and were therefore, another important category in the unit of analysis. At least 6.5% and 4.3% were the deputy headteachers and headteachers respectively. The proportions of the respondents by designation reflects the representativeness of the respondents in the population of study and therefore, the results of the study may be generalized to the entire target population of study in Sebei sub-region.

Influence of Development of Career Opportunities on Dual Career Development

The study sought to establish the influence of development of career opportunities on dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. In order to draw a precise conclusion about this objective, it was prudent to generate and analyze data the completed questionnaires by considering items on development of career opportunities. After analysis, the overall mean from the descriptive statistics was used to generate inferential statistics (linear regression) with the means from the descriptive data on academic and sports career development Therefore, Table 1.3 presents the descriptive statistics on development of career opportunities among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.3: Descriptive Statistics on Development of Career Opportunities among Students in Sec. Schs. In Sebei Sub-region

Items on Development of Career Opportunities among Students	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
In most cases, staff engage in discussing nature of available jobs in order to support students in developing career opportunities	16.2	2.7	50.3	30.8	2.96	.994
When teachers carry out discussions of the nature of future jobs, it helps students to develop interest in available career opportunities	0.0	16.2	45.4	38.4	3.22	.707
By providing information on job requirements, teachers have enabled students to develop interest in various career opportunities	0.5	1.1	65.4	33.0	3.31	.518
Teachers often talk to students about benefits of the various career opportunities in order to support them in making good choices	0.5	0.5	46.5	52.4	3.51	.543
Teachers share the challenges faced in various careers in order to support students in developing career choices	0.5	13.0	53.5	33.0	3.19	.669
Overall Mean					3.24	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0-1.0 = Dev't of career opportunities rarely provided; 1.1-2.0 = Dev't of career opportunities fairly provided; 2.1-3.0 = Dev't of career opportunities moderately provided; 3.1-4.0 = Dev't of career opportunities well provided

Data in Table 1.3 revealed that 50.3% of the respondents agreed and 30.8% of them strongly agreed that in most cases, staff engages in discussing nature of available jobs in order to support students in developing career opportunities. Only a small proportion of respondents disagreed in this regard. This implied that in most of the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, the teachers especially the career teachers engaged the students on issues of developing career opportunities. This was by providing information to students about the available careers and the necessary requirements for getting into those careers. The results further revealed that 45.4% of the respondents agreed and another 38.4% of them strongly agreed that when teachers carried out discussions of the nature of future jobs, it helped students to develop interest in available career opportunities.

The results of the study further indicated that majority (65.4%) of the respondents agreed and 33.0% of them strongly agreed that By providing information on job requirements, teachers have enabled students to develop interest in various career opportunities. A minimal proportion of the respondents disagreed in this regard. Similarly, majority (52.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and 46.5% of them agreed that teachers often talked to students about benefits of the various

career opportunities in order to support them in making good choices. Additionally, majority (53.5%) of the respondents agreed and 33.0% of them strongly agreed that teachers shared the challenges faced in various careers in order to support students in developing career choices. The overall mean for all the items on development of career opportunities was 3.24 which according to the legend implied that development of career opportunities well provided by teachers in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region tried to support students by providing information on career opportunities.

To make an appropriate conclusion about this study, it was prudent to also analyze the collected data on dual career development. The study considered two general careers namely the academic and the sports careers.

Descriptive Statistics on Development of Academic Careers

Table 1.4 presents descriptive statistics on development of academic careers.

Table 1.4: Development of Academic Careers

Items on Development of Academic Careers	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
Most of the students who have passed through this school have ended up as school teachers	15.7	18.9	24.9	40.5	2.90	1.104
The school has produced several medical doctors since its inception	25.9	7.6	41.1	25.4	2.66	1.122
Most of the students aspire to become lawyers	13.0	25.4	49.7	11.9	2.61	.860
Majority of the students in this school would want to be social workers to serve their communities	1.1	33.0	36.8	29.2	2.94	.815
The school has produced a number of people now working as Public Administrators such as Chief Administrative Officers	25.4	50.3	9.7	14.6	2.14	.960
The students in this school aspire to become Engineers of different categories in their future lifetime	0.0	16.8	63.8	19.5	3.03	.603
Students would like to end up as Statisticians working with different organizations dealing with statistics	2.2	35.1	49.7	13.0	2.74	.707
Overall Mean					2.72	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Academic careers not prioritized; 1.1 - 2.0 = Academic careers fairly prioritized;

2.1 - 3.0 = Academic careers moderately prioritized; 3.1-4.0 = Academic careers well prioritized

Data in Table 1.4 revealed that 24.9% and 40.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the students who had passed through the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had ended up as school teachers. However, 18.9% and 15.7% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that most of the students who had passed through the secondary schools had ended up as school teachers. This implied that not all the students who had studied in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had become teachers. The findings further revealed that 41.1% and 25.4% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the schools had produced several medical doctors since their inception. However, 25.9% and 7.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively that the schools had produced several medical doctors since their inception. This too, implied that the schools had not produced several medical doctors, perhaps some few but not several.

Furthermore, the findings showed that 49.7% and 11.9% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the students from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region aspired to become lawyers. Similarly, 36.8% and 29.2% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that majority of the students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region would want to be social workers to serve their communities. However, 50.3% and 25.4% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the secondary schools had produced a number of people now working in the public sector as Public Administrators such as Chief Administrative Officers. This implied that perhaps on few of the students from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had ended up as Public Administrators.

The findings also showed that majority (63.8%) and 19.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the students in the secondary schools aspired to become Engineers of different categories in their future lifetime.

Similarly, majority (49.7% and 13.0% agreed and strongly agreed respectively that students studying in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region would like to end up as Statisticians working with different organizations dealing with statistics. The overall mean for all the items on development of academic careers was 2.72 which according to the legend implied that academic careers moderately prioritized by many student aspiring to take on academic careers for their future life.

Before, considering the influence of development of career opportunities on development of academic careers among the students, it was prudent to ascertain their relatedness. Therefore, the results in Table 1.5 show the relatedness of the development of career opportunities to development of academic careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.5: Relatedness of Development of Career Opportunities to Academic Careers Development in Secondary Schools in Sebei sub-region

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.380	.352		1.081	.281
1 Developing Career Opportunities	.778	.106	.476	7.326	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Academic career development

The results in Table 1.5 indicated a significance value (Sig) of .000 implying that development of career opportunities is significantly related to development of academic careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Influence of Development of Career Opportunities on Academic Careers Development

In order to determine the influence of development of career opportunities on the academic careers development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, a linear regression was run using the transformed the overall means in Table 1.3 (i.e 3.24) for development of career opportunities and that in Table 1.4 (i.e. 2.72) for academic careers development. The results of the linear regression are presented in Table 1.6 and Table 1.7.

Table 1.6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.476 ^a	.227	.223	.973

a. Predictors: (Constant), Developing Career Opportunities

The R square value was .227 which can be converted to percent (.227 x 100) giving 22.7%. This means that for every unit effort in supporting students in development of career opportunities in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, development of academic careers improves by 22.7%. To determine whether or not such a change causes a significant influence, the ANOVA results in Table 1.7 were considered.

Table 1.7: Influence of Development of Career Opportunities on Academic Careers Development among Students in Sec. Schools in Sebei (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	50.852	1	50.852	53.669	.000 ^b
	Residual	173.396	183	.948		
	Total	224.249	184			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic career development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Developing Career Opportunities

The significance (Sig) value was found to be 0.000 which was less than 0.05 (the standard). This implies that there is also a strong significant influence of supporting development of career opportunities and academic careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Descriptive Statistics on Development of Sports Careers

Table 1.8 presents the descriptive statistics on development of sports careers.

Table 1.8: Descriptive Statistics on Development of Sports Careers

Items on Development of Sports Careers	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
There are students who would like to work as Sports Directors in future.	1.6	18.4	51.4	28.6	3.07	.730
Some of the students who completed from this school now work as Sports Managers	15.1	36.2	47.0	1.6	2.35	.752
A number of the students are now working as Directors in the sports field around the country	19.5	51.9	25.9	2.7	2.12	.742
Majority of our students are now Trainers in various sporting activities	2.2	25.9	69.7	2.2	2.72	.539
We have several of our former students who are Referees in the sports field	2.2	19.5	64.9	13.5	2.90	.639
Some of our students would want to work as Umpires for some of the common sports activities in the country	0.5	19.5	51.4	28.6	3.08	.706
Overall Mean					2.71	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Sports careers not prioritized; 1.1 - 2.0 = Sports careers fairly prioritized;

2.1 - 3.0 = Sports careers moderately prioritized; 3.1-4.0 = Sports careers well prioritized

Data in Table 1.8 showed that majority (51.4%) of the respondents agreed and another 28.6% of them strongly agreed that there were students who liked to work as sports directors in future. However, a small proportion of 18.4% disagreed and 1.6% strongly disagreed that there were students who liked to work as sports directors in future. This implied that there were a significant number of students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region who had interest in development of a sports career. The results further showed that 47.0% of the respondents acknowledged that some of the students who completed from the secondary school in Sebei sub-region now work as sports managers. However, another 36.2% disagreed in this regard. This implies that while some of the students who completed from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were already working as sports managers, the others were not. Perhaps they were engaged in other careers.

Furthermore, the results in Table 1.8 revealed that majority (51.9%) of the respondents disagreed with another 19.5% of them strongly disagreeing that a number of the students were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. At least 25.9% and 2.7% of them agreed and strongly agreed respectively that a number of the students were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. This implies that some few of the students who studied in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. The results also indicated that majority (69.7%) of the respondents acknowledged that most of the students were now trainers in various sporting activities. Similarly, majority (64.9%) of the respondents agreed and 13.5% of them strongly agreed that they had several of their former students who were referees in the sports field. Another 51.4% agreed and 28.6% strongly agreed that some of their students would want to work as umpires for some of the common sports activities in the country.

The overall mean for all the items on development of the sports careers was 2.71 which according to the legend implied that sports careers moderately prioritized by many students who aspired to take on sports careers for their future life. Table 1.9 shows the relatedness of the development of career opportunities to development of sports careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.9: Relatedness of Development of Career Opportunities to Sports of Sports Careers Development in Secondary Schools in Sebei sub-region

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.358	.380		-.942	.347
Developing career opportunities	.995	.113	.547	8.844	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sports career development

The significance value (Sig) of .000 implying that development of career opportunities is also significantly related to sports careers development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Regression Analysis for Influence of Development of Career Opportunities on Sports Careers Development

In order to determine the influence of development of career opportunities on the sports careers development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, a linear regression was run using the transformed the overall means in Table 1.3 (i.e 3.24) for development of career opportunities and that in Table 1.8 (i.e. 2.71) for sports careers development. The results of the linear regression are presented in Table 1.10 and Table 1.11.

Table 1.10: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.547 ^a	.299	.296	.834

a. Predictors: (Constant), Developing career opportunities

The R square value in Table 1.10 was .299 which can be converted to percent (.299 x 100) giving 29.9%. This means that for every unit change in supporting students in development of career opportunities in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, sports careers development improves by 29.9%. To determine whether or not such a change causes a significant influence, the ANOVA results in Table 1.11 were considered.

Table 1.11: Influence of Support in Development of Career Opportunities on Sports Careers Development among Students in Sec. Schools in Sebei (ANOVA)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	54.390	1	54.390	78.211	.000 ^b
Residual	127.264	183	.695		
Total	181.654	184			

a. Dependent Variable: Sports career development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Developing career opportunities

The significance (Sig) value was found to be .000 which was less than 0.05 (the standard). This implies that there is also a strong significant influence of supporting development of career opportunities and sports careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

The quantitative results for development of both academic and sports careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were closely in agreement with the qualitative data gathered through face-to-face interviews with several participants. For instance, in a face-to-face interview with one of the deputy headteachers of the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region (R-DHT-01) said:

“Development of career opportunities can enable the learners to concentrate on one career at a time a case in point is Joshua Cheptegei who had to leave academics for a while and is currently concentrating on the sports career. This implies that the student can concentrate on the sports which is time bound leaving academic career which is continuous and can be of benefit when one retires from sports career. However, through development of career opportunities, the student can be in position to concentrate on one career and intern he/she doesn't market in the career and this can cause total frustration to the student. In that regard, the students appear with multiple careers but through development of career opportunities the student is able to specialize to one career.”

In another interview, the director of studies (R-DOS-01) said:

“I acknowledge that students have opportunity to develop their careers through the following: through participation in both academic and sports; being encouraged to actively participate in career activity at given times; being provided with a list of role models for better influence; through regular competition both within the school, inter school, district and national level; and through guidance and counselling.”

In a face-to-face interview with a headteacher (R-HT-02), he said:

“First, it presents a challenge because teachers have less skills about career guidance and if they have any, then they have very little time allocated to it. Also, many teachers are negligent to guide the learners. Lastly, the instructional materials for both the academic and sports part are not adequate enough teachers still have a lay man’s mode at teaching without career guidance since they themselves were not guided.”

Similarly, in response to the issue of development of career opportunities and dual career development among students, one of the directors of studies (R-DOS-03) said:

“Career development had influenced dual career development to a lower extend most students are now engaged in sports as well as academics. Many learners have now entered music industry yet they cannot fore go their studies. Such learners end up succeeding in both.”

Similarly another director of studies (R-DOS-04) said:

“The impact is positively since the learners get additions advantage of succeeding in either of the two. It mostly improve the child’s discipline since most activities require discipline especially football ragbag, netball and athletics.”

This implied first that there was opportunity for career development while in the schools and second that such opportunity had influenced and also impacted on dual career development among the students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. With more interviews carried out, yet another director of studies (R-DOS-05) said:

“Assisting students to develop career opportunities enhances performance in individual subjects resulting into better grades that the quality learners for their careers. At the end, there will be attainment of discipline among learners which enhance performance, since they will be empowered with the knowledge of research, which builds their content in the learning field. It also encourages or builds the four aspects of use as in the Ego connectedness, psycho-motor and the attentiveness - which increase the retention concept which can lead to brain drain or lack of content.”

The face-to-face interviews further revealed similar information about dual career development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. As far as the items on issues of development of career opportunities among students were concerned, more of the participants acknowledged that the students had the opportunity of career development in the schools. In that regard, one of the deputy headteachers (R-DHT-04) said:

“Developing opportunities helps the learner to know as well as prepare to excel in both talent and academics other can even do more than two.”

Similarly, a director of studies (R-DOS-06) who claimed he had worked with the headteacher to ensure students’ were provided with opportunity of career development said:

“Providing opportunity for students to develop careers enables teachers and learners to participate in both academics and sport at ago. But at the end come up with the one can do best. It also helps to reduce frustrations on the side of those who may fail in either of the two sport and academics. Such a learner is most likely to succeed in one.”

During the face-to-face interviews with participants, it was also revealed that sports offices in the three districts of Kapchorwa, Kween and Bukwo were often involved in activities geared at developing students’ career opportunities. However, when interviewed, the sports officers indicated that there were often a clash in student’s interests in dual career development. Indeed, one of the sports officers (R-SO-03) said:

“Sport and academics sometimes may not rhyme together. In most cases those who are good in sports are not good in academics. This means that it’s difficult to balance the two.”

Yet another sports officer (R-SO-01) said:

“When learners acquire with information about career opportunities available to them they can be enhanced to a dual career system. This is because they will appreciate the value of each opportunity in ones future life. The students will have been advised along dual career, they tend to get a wide network of friends, who then directs one to fully accept to peruse dual career opportunities.”

This implied that development of career opportunities is provided to the students in the secondary schools in the region. However, according to information obtained through face-to-face interviews with directors of studies, it was revealed that some students had challenges dealing with both academic and sports career development. One of the directors of studies (R-DOS-05) said:

“Most students may not handle sport and academics smoothly. Those who are good in sports may not be doing very well in academics except very isolated cases like Joshua Cheptegei. Above all some learners themselves are negligent to heed to advice and do as they please. This hampers dual careers. The school setting itself hampers the dual careers for example a student in S.2 can be having a donkey to transport form produce to the market. Some also value more their farming projects more than academics and sports most students in the rural setting are day scholars at the time they reach home, they interact with their friends who mislead them. A case in point is a boy who was very good in athletics but was misguided by his friend now is a farmer deep in the village.”

Data collected through face-to-face interviews also revealed that secondary schools in the region always endeavoured to organize occasions where students would be provided with opportunity for career development. For instance, one of the respondent headteachers of the secondary schools (R-HT-03) said:

“Careers are always organized internally and role models are invited to inspire students and talk about barriers towards different fields. Professionals in like the DHO and the Principal of Kapchorwa Technical Institute have often been invited. However, what I have noted is that the impact is a positive one. The learner’s mindset can be changed especially through the testimonies of role models who once hail from low economic backgrounds. They are also motivated to take sport and academics more seriously. Some students have been able to make it in both like in sport and academics. Unfortunately, the number of students who excel in both sports and academics is much smaller than those who excel in one.”

On the other hand, it was discovered that as a way to improve on dual career development among the students in the secondary schools, management of the schools has decided to offer bursaries to some students. For instance one of the deputy headteachers (R-DHT-04) said:

“We provide opportunity to develop dual among students by giving bursaries to those excel in both sports and academics. A case in point is that of Stella Chesang who is a known Ugandans Gold medalist. She was given bursaries from S.1-S.4 by Chemwaphia High school and was able to build her talent. Stella Chesang would have stopped in S.1 but bursaries helped her and she can read and write. This has given her an upper hand to hold the position she holds in the public.”

However, another director of studies lamented that fact that even when opportunity for career development is provided, some students still find challenges. For instance, the director of studies (R-DOS-02) said:

“Most learners cannot balance the sport and academics. Student Athletes in the school setting look at role models like Joshua Chapegei and they think, that is all they want to be. Therefore, they spend most of the time in sporting. The balance in terms of time between class work and sport is not easy. Also, some students concentrate their energy in class work rather than in sports activities.”

The participants explained the importance of sporting in promoting academics among the students. One of the headteachers (R-HT-06) said:

“Sport refreshes the learner’s brain and removes boredom from class as he proverb goes ‘Too much work without play makes jack and Jill boy.’ Makes learners to be healthy which arises out of physical exercise which boosts the health of a student making him or her sharper in academics. There for the two work currently.”

Yet another headteachers (R-HT-04) explained and compared his students to some role models in the country. He said:

“Development of career needs enables learners to develop more other career opportunities at their disposal for example a student who has identified athletics can as well choose to take a medical profession or Music, Dance and Drama like Robert Kyagulanyi is a Musician as well as lawyer.”

This implied that it would be easy to of the two since it's mostly done at hoe especially now that most schools in the rural setting are day. What school heads need to do s allocate a reasonable vote to career guidance especially sport. The qualitative data collected provided a triangulation to the descriptive statistics presented in the tables. The respondent headteachers, deputy headteachers and directors of studies all acknowledged the importance of provision of career development opportunities to the students.

5. DISCUSSION

Accordingly, they indicated that career development allows individuals to discover who they are, what they like to do and what they do best. Their opinions corroborated with the findings of other studies elsewhere. For instance, it had been indicated that balancing between two different commitments, sport and education, has been demonstrated as one of the significant challenges for dual career athletes, namely student athletes (European Commission, 2012). Research has emphasized that it is integral to understand DC athletes' lives at a different stage and development (Graczyk, Wylleman, Nawrocka, Atroszko, Moska et al., 2017). A dual career is defined as an integration of sport with academic or vocational work, which can provide benefits (e.g. social, health-related, developmental, and financial) (Harrison, Vickers, Fletcher, & Tylor, 2020; Reints, 2011) to athletes during their sporting career and after transitioning out of sport (European Commission, 2007, 2012). In the Duty of Care in Sport Review (2017), it is highlighted that schools should be informed to enable them support talented young athletes who are pursuing DCs.

The findings of the study indicated that majority of the respondents agreed that in most cases, the teachers, particularly the teachers in charge of career guidance were engaged in discussing nature of available jobs in order to support students in developing career opportunities. Furthermore, the findings revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that the teachers shared the challenges faced in various careers in order to support students in developing career choices.

The findings also showed that development of career opportunities was significantly related to development of academic careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. For instance, the findings indicated that for every unit effort in supporting students in development of career opportunities in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, development of academic careers improved by 22.7%. This implied that there was a strong significant influence of teachers' supporting development of career opportunities on academic careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

As far as the sporting careers were concerned, the findings of the study indicated that development of career opportunities was significantly related to sports careers development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. For instance, the findings indicated that for every unit effort in supporting students in development of career opportunities in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, sports careers development improved by 29.9%. This implied that there was a strong significant influence of supporting development of career opportunities on sports careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Considering the magnitude of influence, supporting students in development of career opportunities in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had a higher magnitude of influence for sports than for academic career development. Influence on sports career development was one and a half times (29.9% to 22.7%) higher than for academic career development. This means that out of every ten (10) students supported in the development of career, six (6) would choose to engage in a sports career development while only four (4) would choose to engage in an academic career development.

6. CONCLUSIONS

From the findings of the study and corresponding discussion, the study concluded that there was a strong significant influence of teachers' supporting development of career opportunities on academic careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. There was also a strong significant influence of supporting development of career opportunities on sports careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. However, given the same support towards development of career opportunities, more students would be more likely choose a sports

career for development than an academic career. Out of every ten (10) students supported in the development of career, six (6) would choose to engage in a sports career development while only four (4) would choose to engage in an academic career development. In conclusion, teachers' supporting of development of career has a stronger influence towards sports career development than academic development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The career guidance teachers need to be appropriately informed about the processes that lead to development of career opportunities among individuals.
- ii. Career education should be included in the school curriculum in order to provide appropriate connection to the wider school curriculum.
- iii. Career education should be provided at all levels of education and harmonized to ensure that specific information reaches out to all students and should be in tandem with possible careers for the students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bamberg, M. (2011). Who am I? Narration and its contribution to self and identity. *Theory & Psychology*, 21(1), 3–24.
- [2] Bamberg, M., & Georgakopoulou, A. (2008). Small stories as a new perspective in narrative and identity analysis. *Text & Talk*, 28(3), 377–396.
- [3] Bandura, A., (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action : a social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall.
- [4] Bandura, A. (1988). Organizational Application of Social Cognitive Theory. *Australian Journal of Management*. 13 (2): 275–302.
- [5] Bandura, A. (1989). Human Agency in Social Cognitive Theory. *American Psychologist*. 44 (9): 1175–1184.
- [6] Carless, D., & Douglas, K. (2013). Living, resisting, and playing the part of athlete: Narrative tensions in elite sport. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 14(5), 701–708.
- [7] Cosh, S., & Tully, P. J. (2014). “All I have to do is pass”: A discursive analysis of student athletes' talk about prioritising sport to the detriment of education to overcome stressors encountered in combining elite sport and tertiary education. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 15(2), 180–189.
- [8] Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research* (5th. ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- [9] DEO Registry (2021). Statistical Returns from Schools in Kapchorwa District. Kapchorwa District Local Government. Kapchorwa.
- [10] DEO Registry (2021). Statistical Returns from Schools in Kween District. Kween District Local Government. Kween .
- [11] DEO Registry (2021). Statistical Returns from Schools in Bukwo District. Bukwo District Local Government. Bukwo .
- [12] De Vaus, D. (2002) *Surveys in Social Research*. 5th Edition, Routledge, London.
- [13] Dillman, P. (2000). Human rights in youth sport: a critical review of children's rights in competitive sports. *Human rights in youth sport: a critical review of children's rights in competitive sports*.
- [14] Douglas, K., & Carless, D. (2009). Abandoning the performance narrative: Two women's stories of transition from professional sport. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 21, 213–230.
- [15] Douglas, K., & Carless, D. (2015). *Life story research in sport: Understanding the experiences of elite and professional athletes through narrative*. London: Routledge.

- [16] Erikson, E. H. (2018). *Identity: Youth and crisis*. New York: Norton & Company. EU guidelines on dual careers of athletes: Recommended policy actions in support of dual careers in high performance sport.
- [17] ESSP (2017). *Education And Sports Sector Strategic Plan (ESSP)*: Ministry of Education and Sports, Republic of Uganda. Kampala.
- [18] European Commission. (2007). *White Paper on Sport*. Brussels: Directorate General for Education and Culture.
- [19] European Union (2012). *Guidelines on dual careers of athletes: Recommended policy actions in support of dual careers in high performance sport*.
- [20] Fivush, R. (2010). Speaking silence: The social construction of silence in autobiographical and cultural narratives. *Memory*, 18(2), 88–98.
- [21] George, D., & Mallery, P. (2003). *SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference. 11.0 update* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- [22] Glenn, D. I. (1992). Sampling the Evidence of Extension Program Impact. Program Evaluation and Organizational Development, IFAS, University of Florida.
- [23] Gysberg, C. N., Heppner, M. J., & Johnston, J. A. (1998). *Career counseling: Process, issues and techniques*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- [24] Hammack, P. L. (2008). Narrative and the cultural psychology of identity. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 12(3), 222–247.
- [25] Hammersley, M. (1987). Some notes on the terms 'validity' and 'reliability'. *British Educational Research Journal*, 13(1), 73-81.
- [26] Harrison, G.E., Vickers, E., Fletcher, D., & Taylor, G. (2020). Elite female soccer players' dual career plans and the demands they encounter. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*.
- [27] Kothari C.R (2006), *Research methodology*. New Age International Publishers Limited India.
- [28] Lemeni, S., & Mihalcea, E. (2005). Guiding students into the future: Three schools of thought. In M. Csikszentmihalyi & B. Schneider (Eds.), *Becoming adult: How teenagers prepare for the world of work* (pp. 167-98). NY: Basic Books.
- [29] Marshall, C. and Rossman, G.B. (1999) *Designing Qualitative Research*. 3rd Edition, International Educational and Professional Publisher, California, 35.
- [30] McAdams, D. P. (2008). Personal narratives and the life story. In O. P. John, R. W. Robins, & L. A. Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 242–262). New York: Guilford Press.
- [31] McGannon, K., Tatarnic, E., & McMahon, J. (2019). The long and winding road: An autobiographic study of an elite athlete mother's journey to winning gold. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 31, 385–404.
- [32] McLean, K. C., & Syed, M. (2016). Personal, master, and alternative narratives: An integrative framework for understanding identity development in context. *Human Development*, 58(6), 318–349
- [33] NCDC (2017). National Curriculum Development Centre (NCDC) Report: Ministry of Education and Sports. Kyambogo.
- [34] NCDC (2020). National Curriculum Development Centre (NCDC) Report: Ministry of Education and Sports. Kyambogo.
- [35] Nurmi, J. E. (2004). Socialization and self-development: Channelling, selection, adjustment and reflection. In R. Lerner, & L. Steinberg (Eds.), *Handbook of adolescent psychology* (pp. 85–124). New York, NY: Wiley.
- [36] OECD (2010), *Career Guidance and Public Policy: Bridging the Gap*, Paris.
- [37] OECD (2018). Educational and career guidance: What works. *OECDObserver*, 202: 37-40.

- [38] O'Neill, M., Allen, B., & Calder, A. (2013). Pressures to perform: An interview study of Australian high performance school-age athletes' perceptions of balancing their school and sporting lives. *Performance Enhancement & Health*, 2, 87–93.
- [39] Otwine, A. and Oonyu, J. (2018). Career Guidance and Counselling in Uganda. Current Developments and challenges. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*; November 2018.
- [40] Pajares, F. (2009). "Social cognitive theory and media effects". *The Sage Handbook of Media Processes and Effects*: 283–297.
- [41] Reints, A. (2011). *Validation of the holistic athletic career model and the identification of variables related to athletic retirement*. Vubpress.
- [42] Ritchie, J., & Lewis, J. (2003). *Qualitative Research Practice—A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. London, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Ltd.
- [43] Rugangila, M. K. (2019). The impact of extracurricular athletic activities on academic achievement, disciplinary referrals, and school attendance among Hispanic female 11th Grade students. *Dissertations Publishing*, ProQuest.
- [44] Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research methods for business students*. 2nd Ed. Harlow, Essex: Pearson Education.
- [45] Seale, G. (1999). Objectively yours, Michel Foucault. *Educational Theory*, 48(1), 59-66.
- [46] Smith, P., & Bond, M., H. (2008). *Social psychology across cultures, second edition*. London: Prentice Hall
- [47] Spector-Mersel, G. (2006). Never-aging stories: Western hegemonic masculinity scripts. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 15(1), 67–82.
- [48] Swann, B., Moran, G.W., & Piggott, B.A. (2015). *The impact of a career course on retention and academic performance*. Technical Report 34. Tallahassee, FL: Career Center, Florida State University.
- [49] Taras, H. (2005). *Physical Activity and Student Performance at School*. Routledge, London.
- [50] Urich, A. (2017). Social Cognitive Theory. Methods for Stress Management. Retrieved 2021-06-21
- [51] USPA (2019). Uganda Sports Association Annual Report: Ministry of Education and Sports. Kampala.
- [52] Winter, G. (2000). A Comparative Discussion of the Notion of Validity. Discussion of Qualitative and Quantitative Research. University of Manchester, England.
- [53] Yiannakis, P., & Melnick, C. (2001). *Influence of school practices on students' academic choices*. Research Triangle Park, NC: RTI and Atlanta: Southern Regional Education Board.